

**THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE ANALYSIS OF OBSTACLES
TO THE REALIZATION OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS**

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The history of the protection of women's rights at the international level is connected with the development of the protection of the rights and freedoms of the whole person. The beginning of the XX century was marked exclusively by domestic regulation of issues related to human rights, since countries believed that the consolidation of individual rights was part of their internal competence. However, many universal international treaties have established the most important provisions "for the protection of women's rights and have become the basis for international standards for the protection of these rights."

The Statute of the League of Nations stipulated "the requirement to ensure equal conditions for all people, regardless of gender and age, as well as a ban on trafficking in women and children." The League of Nations planned to "conduct research on the status of women, including legal issues, in various countries of the world, cooperating with relevant organizations and creating an ad hoc committee of experts." However, the outbreak of World War II prevented the implementation of this initiative.

Article 3 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 regulates the obligations of States parties to ensure the equal right to enjoy all civil and political rights, as well as all economic, social and cultural rights provided for in both Covenants for both men and women.

In life, representatives of the female sex face some problems, such as harassment, domestic violence. Statistics were developed by the World Bank:

- 2.4 billion do not have equal economic opportunities;
- there are legal barriers in 178 countries;
- in 86 countries, women have a work restriction;
- 95 countries do not pay for equal work .

In addition, these statistics show that at the moment women have only three-quarters of the rights that men have (76.5/100%).

"Despite some progress, the gap between the expected earnings of men and women during their lifetime is 172 trillion globally. US dollars is almost 2 times the world GDP per year," said Marie Pangestu, Managing Director of the World Bank for Development Policy and Partnerships.

The danger is not excluded, so far, many countries are against the adoption of a law on domestic violence. There remain countries where the factors of abuse, early marriage of minors, gender-based violence are deeply preserved, in addition, there are many other factors that infringe on women's rights, for example, threats and violence in social networks.

Closer to 2022, 3/4 of the countries agreed to adopt laws in support of women. Violence, forced marriages, social problems, political restrictions and legal infringements have significantly decreased in those countries. One of the achievements is that many countries have stopped cruel surgical procedures on female genitals.

There is an active propaganda of "not silence", according to which women and girls are asked not to be silent about their violated rights and demand their realization.

Let's describe the theoretical results of the problems of gender inequality:

1. In global healthcare, women actually provide many services, while men predominate in senior management positions. This unequal gender balance is mainly due to stereotypes, discrimination and limited equal opportunities. Some women also face infringement of their rights due to racial or class persecution.

2. This inequality in health care management is a problem of equity and efficiency. Women should also be able to lead and make decisions in this area, taking into account their experience and knowledge. Increasing the proportion of women in global health leadership can lead to a broader representation of the health needs of women and girls, as well as more effective strategies to combat global health problems.

3. Cultural labels play an important role in why women so rarely occupy leadership positions in the field of healthcare. There is a widespread prejudice that women are better suited for the role of medical professionals, rather than for leadership positions, which can lead to inequality in opportunities and wages. In addition, there is discrimination based on gender, where women can be persecuted or excluded from senior positions in healthcare just because of their gender. All this is confirmed by recent studies that show that women in healthcare often face obstacles in their work, such as wage inequality, lack of support, fewer opportunities for professional development and opportunities for career advancement. As a result, a small number of women in the leadership of global health can lead to a decrease in the effectiveness of strategies to combat global health problems, such as the spread of infectious diseases, increased maternal and newborn mortality, etc.

4. Women in healthcare often face wage discrimination, which leads to wage inequality and career opportunities. This may manifest itself in the form of lower salaries, a lower probability of getting a promotion or promotion on the career ladder, as well as limited access to training and support in professional development. As a result, this limits women's opportunities in healthcare and creates barriers to their promotion to leadership positions in this area. In addition, unpaid work also has a significant impact on gender equality in health care. Many medical workers, mostly female, are often forced to perform unpaid work, such as volunteering, voluntary training and work within the family, which can lead to even lower income and fewer opportunities for professional development.

5. It is very important to raise awareness and support women in the workplace. Organizations can create training programs, seminars and forums for women so that they can improve their skills and confidence, which will help them move up the career ladder. It is also necessary to organize special units or support services so that women can seek help in case of discrimination or sexual harassment. Trade unions also have an important role to play in protecting women from violations and fighting for rights in the workplace. All these measures will help female healthcare workers not only feel safe and secure at work, but also have equal opportunities to develop a professional career.

6. To solve this problem, it is necessary to improve women's access to vocational training and advanced training, as well as to create equal opportunities for women and men in all aspects of professional activity. Along with this, it is necessary to improve legislation in the field of gender equality and combat discrimination in the workplace. It is also important to improve working conditions and wages for all medical workers, including women. Solving these problems in healthcare will help attract and retain talented and motivated workers, which in turn will have a positive impact on the quality of healthcare and the availability of medical services for everyone, especially for vulnerable groups of the population.

7. In order to combat gender-based discrimination, it is necessary to carry out educational work and cover the problem in the media. It is also necessary to strengthen legislation to ensure the protection of people's rights to equal access to education, work and health care, regardless of their gender. Awareness-raising campaigns should also be carried out so that society is aware of gender inequalities and advanced ideas on how to overcome them and how to unite the strengths of men and women in the fight against this problem.

8. gender discrimination, when women are not given equal opportunities in education, work and politics on the basis of their gender. This can lead to low employment, low pay and insufficient access to career opportunities. Violence and harassment are also a serious problem for women. Many women face this form of infringement of rights, and this can lead to physical and psychological problems, damage to self-esteem and limited opportunities to communicate with other people. In addition, it is important to take into account the socio-cultural characteristics and the context in which the research is conducted, and adhere to the principles of ethics and fairness. Research results should be accessible and understandable to a wide audience, including decision makers and civil society. In general, scientific research should play a key role in the formation and implementation of gender policy and social programs aimed at achieving gender equality and preventing discrimination based on gender identity.

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